

PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF ENDO AND MYOMETRY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ABNORMAL UTERINE BLEEDING IN WOMEN.

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Aim: Purpose of this study to determine the pathomorphological causes of abnormal uterine bleeding in perimenopausal women.

Materials and methods :To achieve our goal, we examined 55 perimenopausal women with abnormal uterine bleeding who underwent the following examination methods: anamnesis and assessment of the nature of bleeding, clinical blood test, gynecological examination ,color doppler mapping, curettage of the uterine cavity with subsequent histology , hysteroscopy with targeted biopsy and histology.

Results of the study and their discussion: The age of women varied from 45 to 49 years. From the anamnesis of relapse, abnormal uterine bleeding was observed in 15 (27%) women. In the remaining 40 (72%). In 6 (11%) women, on bimanual examination, the size of the uterus was within the normal range, the appendages were not palpable. In 36 (65%), the size of the uterus during bimanual examination was increased in size, in 25 (69%) of them, pain was also observed during the examination. In 13 (24%) women, an increase in the uterus and appendages was observed. Laboratory evaluation included a clinical blood count and a coagulogram. All examined women had anemia of various degrees, of which severe anemia was observed in 15 (27%). Blood coagulation disorder was in 5(9%), 4(80%) of them were towards hypercoagulation, and 1(20%) - hypocoagulation. Curettage of the uterine cavity with subsequent histology was performed in 35 (64%) of the examined patients in order to diagnose and stop bleeding. Histological responses were as follows: glandular hyperplasia of the endometrium in 11 (31.5%) patients, glandular cystic hyperplasia in 6 (17%) patients, endometrial polyposis in 9 (25%), atypical hyperplasia in 1 (3%), endometrial cancer in 1 (3%), in the remaining 7 (20%), an inflammatory process of the endometrium was revealed.

Conclusion: According to the results of pathomorphological studies, the most common causes of abnormal uterine bleeding in perimenopause are endometrial hyperplastic processes (36%), which are often combined with

adenomyosis and uterine myoma (20.8%). The most informative methods of examination were Doppler ultrasound, diagnostic curettage of the uterine cavity.

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